

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION CENTERS OF THE FEDERAL INSTITUTES AS A TOOL FOR PROMOTING TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION IN BRAZIL

NÚCLEO DE INNOVACIÓN TECNOLÓGICA DE INSTITUTOS FEDERALES COMO INSTRUMENTO PARA FOMENTAR LA INNOVACIÓN TECNOLÓGICA EN BRASIL

NÚCLEOS DE INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA DOS INSTITUTOS FEDERAIS COMO INSTRUMENTO DE FOMENTO A INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA NO BRASIL

Ayalla Oliveira Chaves ¹
Gustavo Pereira da Cruz ²
Thiago Ferreira de Sousa ³

Manuscript received on: April 17, 2024.

Approved on: September 29, 2024.

Published on: February 6, 2025.

Abstract

As key agents responsible for managing scientific and technological outputs within the Federal Institutes of Education (FI), the Technology Transfer Offices (TTO) play a vital role in fostering intellectual development, thereby advancing science and technology across Brazil. This study seeks to characterize the activities of TTO within FIs, particularly in relation to research development, intellectual property management, and their contributions to promoting innovation and technology transfer (TT). Of the 38 existing FIs in Brazil, 15 participated in the survey, which involved administering a questionnaire designed to gather structural and performance-related data concerning the TTOs. The findings reveal that the average operational duration of the TTO is approximately 7.33 years, with an average workforce of 5.6 employees, often constrained by limited infrastructure within the FIs. Moreover, the most utilized TT mechanisms were found to be: 28.6% through contracts or agreements with other educational and/or research promotion institutions, 25.9% through the establishment of technology-based incubators, and 20% via training courses. Nevertheless, the frequency of industry-academia partnerships remains notably low. In conclusion, one of the primary activities of the TTO is the formation of partnerships with other institutions, either through formal agreements or the creation of technological support spaces. It is imperative to invest in enhancing the structure of TTO to better safeguard the intellectual property of FI and facilitate TT, thereby contributing to national economic development.

Keywords: Research; Intellectual property; Technology transfer.

¹ Master in Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer for Innovation from the State University of Santa Cruz. Public Servant at the Federal University of Southern Bahia.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6376-2462> Contact: ayalla.chaves@gmail.com

² Doctorate in Tourism and Sustainability from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, with a Post-Doctorate in Technology Transfer and Innovation - University of Birmingham. Professor of the Master's Degree in Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer for Innovation at the State University of Santa Cruz.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6525-1298> Contact: dacruz7777@gmail.com

³ Doctorate in Physical Education from the Federal University of Santa Catarina. Professor in the Postgraduate Program in Physical Education at the State University of Santa Cruz.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9846-9661> Contact: tfsousa_thiago@yahoo.com.br

Resumen

Los agentes responsables de gestionar las producciones científicas y tecnológicas de los Institutos Federales de Educación (IFEs), los Centros de Innovación Tecnológica (CITs) contribuyen a promover el desarrollo intelectual generando ciencia y tecnología para el país. Este estudio tiene como objetivo caracterizar las actividades de los CITs de los IFEs en el desarrollo de la investigación y sus relaciones con la propiedad intelectual en la promoción de la innovación y la transferencia de tecnología (TT). De las 38 IFEs de Brasil, 15 participaron de la investigación en la que se aplicó un cuestionario sobre información estructural y el desempeño de los CITs. Los CITs tienen aproximadamente 7,33 años de funcionamiento, operando con una plantilla promedio de 5,6 empleados, con infraestructura limitada dentro de los IFEs. También se identificó que las herramientas de TT más utilizadas por las IFEs son: 28.6% para contratos/acuerdos con otras instituciones educativas y/o para promover la investigación, 25.9% para la creación de incubadoras de base tecnológica y 20% para un curso de capacitación, aunque la frecuencia con la que se producen las actividades de colaboración empresa-escuela sigue siendo irrelevante. De esta manera, es posible concluir que una de las principales actividades de los CITs fueron las alianzas con otras instituciones, ya sea a través del establecimiento de un convenio o espacio de apoyo tecnológico. Es fundamental invertir en una mejor estructuración de las CITs, con el objetivo de proteger la propiedad intelectual de las IFEs y TT que colaboran con el desarrollo económico nacional.

Palabras clave: Investigación; Propiedad intelectual; Transferencia tecnológica.

Resumo

Agentes responsáveis pela gestão das produções científicas tecnológicas dos Institutos Federais de Educação (IFs), os Núcleos de Inovação Tecnológica (NITs) contribuem para promoção do desenvolvimento intelectual gerando ciência e tecnologia para o país. Este estudo tem como objetivo caracterizar as atividades dos NITs dos IF no desenvolvimento da pesquisa e suas relações com a propriedade intelectual no fomento a inovação e transferência de tecnologia (TT). Dos 38 IFs existentes no Brasil, 15 participaram da pesquisa na qual foi aplicado questionário abordando informações estruturais e atuação dos NITs. Os resultados apontam que os NITs têm um tempo de atuação aproximado de 7,33 anos, atuando com quadro de pessoal em média de 5,6 colaboradores, com infraestrutura limitada dentro dos IFs. Identificou-se ainda que as ferramentas mais utilizadas para TT dos IFs foram: 28,6% para contrato/convênio com outras instituições de ensino e/ou de fomento à pesquisa, 25,9% para criação de incubadoras de base tecnológica e 20% para curso de capacitação, apesar de ainda ser irrelevante a frequência com que ocorrem as atividades de parcerias empresa-escola. Desta forma, é possível concluir que uma das principais atividades dos NITs foram as parcerias com outras instituições, seja pelo estabelecimento de convênio ou espaço de suporte tecnológico. É imprescindível investir em melhor estruturação dos NITs, visando à proteção da propriedade intelectual dos IFs e a TT colaborando com desenvolvimento econômico nacional.

Palavras-chave: Pesquisa; Propriedade Intelectual; Transferência de Tecnologia.

Introduction

A means to enhance technological capacity, investment in Research and Development (R&D), policies to promote the formation of a skilled workforce, and the encouragement of technology transfer (TT) represent key strategies that can be adopted (Almeida et al., 2011). Universities, businesses, and the government are the

main stakeholders in the national system for generating and appropriating knowledge (Cruz, 2000).

In innovation systems with an open approach, R&D investment is of great importance. In Brazil, however, the government is the primary investor rather than the private sector, contrasting sharply with the patterns observed in developed countries (Soares et al., 2016).

While Brazil excels in producing scientific knowledge, this output is largely directed towards the publication of academic articles (Garcez Júnior et al., 2016). Given its expenditures on R&D, high-tech net imports and exports, and the quality of its scientific publications, Brazil ranks 49th in the Global Innovation Index (GII) (OMPI, 2023).

Developing countries like Brazil adopt a set of educational policies aimed at improving quality of life by reducing poverty, consolidating democratic values, fostering sustainable economic growth, and increasing social investment (Prada; Garcia, 2016). Education, in this context, serves as an integrative tool for social transformation through the productive use of work.

In recent years, the restructuring of public policies for science, technology, and innovation (ST&I), as well as the expansion of higher and technological education, has contributed significantly to the Brazilian innovation system (Almeida et al., 2011). According to Cruz (2000), in Brazil, there is an expectation that universities will be responsible for promoting the necessary innovation to enhance the competitiveness of businesses.

With the aim of providing technical education and professional qualifications, the Federal Institutes (FI) of Education emerged as part of the Federal Network of Professional, Scientific, and Technological Education (RFEPT), established through Law No. 11,892/2008. Perucchi (2012) highlights that technological education, together with science and technology, plays a prominent role in qualifying human resources for a new development model.

RFEPT is understood as a mechanism to bridge theoretical, scientific, political, and technological studies, enabling an understanding of modern production methods and developing human capabilities to navigate the labor market, as well as to explore students' potential career paths (Moura, 2007; Salviani, 2007; Mancordia, 2011; Aguiar; Pacheco, 2017, as cited in Mota, 2018c).

Beyond technical education, the FI were equated with Federal Universities (FU) at the time of their establishment, adhering to the same criteria for regulation, evaluation, and supervision (Brasil, 2008). Faculty members at FU and FI are required to produce scientific output that results in products, processes, and services to drive local socio-economic development (Perucchi; Garcia, 2012).

It is essential to re-evaluate how scientific knowledge from educational institutions is integrated and transformed into market innovations that add value to industries, effectively involving key players in the triple helix: government, academia, and business. Despite recognition of the need to transfer publicly funded research results to society, in Brazil, this process often encounters operational challenges due to the lack of clear policies on TT (Fujino; Stal, 2007).

From a legal standpoint, there have been advancements in protecting intellectual property (IP) rights and ensuring that creators retain rights over the technological innovations they develop. Noteworthy legislation includes Law No. 9,279/1996, regulating industrial property rights; Law No. 10,973/2004, which promotes innovation and scientific and technological research within the productive environment; and Law No. 13,243/2016, which introduces measures to stimulate scientific development and innovation, as well as the mandatory establishment of Technological Innovation Centers (TIC).

Considering these points, it is vital to assess whether the actions carried out by TIC contribute to a conducive environment for promoting IP and TT. Therefore, the question arises: what is the role of TIC as instruments for promoting technological innovation in Brazil? This study aims to characterize the activities of FI-TIC in research development and their relationship with IP in fostering innovation and TT.

There is a notable lack of information regarding the structural resources available, operational timeframe, organizational structure, competencies, and projects undertaken by TIC in support of research in the productive environment. Understanding the characteristics of FI-TIC may enable stakeholders to identify strengths and weaknesses to better align strategic actions for research aimed at innovation. FI and

their TIC are strategic components of the scientific, technological, IP, and TT development process.

- IP landscape in Brazil

To leverage the country's potential, a cultural transformation towards technological innovation is sought. Data from the Innovation Survey (PINTEC, 2021) indicates growth in the acquisition of R&D by participating companies through external partners-private companies, universities, or research institutes-despite a decrease in internal R&D investment, in contrast to a significant increase in government support for R&D.

Pires, Quintella, and Godinho (2023) note that in Brazil, various laws and policies have been implemented to strengthen ST&I, aiming to foster collaboration between universities and companies and to promote an environment conducive to innovation. In this context, funding research with innovative technological potential is crucial for the economic and social development of Brazil (FINEP, 2023).

The National Strategy for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NSSTI) 2016-2022 prioritizes modernizing and expanding ST&I infrastructure, especially through the commercialization of public research and knowledge transfer, stimulating the marketing of technologies developed in universities and public research institutes (MCTI, 2016).

Innovation within universities drives the development of products and processes, meeting industry and societal demands, and significantly impacting the country's economic development (Pires; Quintella; Godinho, 2023). Interaction between Science and Technology Institutions (STIs) and companies forms the basis for effective TT from academia, creating a competitive advantage and contributing to national economic growth (Soares et al., 2016).

To establish fundamental principles regarding conduct in Brazilian innovation, the Technological Innovation Law (LIT) was created in 2004, regulated by Law No. 10,973. It serves as a tool to encourage interaction between STIs and businesses, and: "Establishes measures to promote innovation and scientific and technological research

in the productive environment, aiming at technological capacity building, achieving technological autonomy, and developing the national and regional production system of the country" (Brasil, 2004).

Since the enactment of LIT, STIs have been required to create their own TIC, as stipulated: "To support the management of their innovation policy, public STIs must have a Technological Innovation Nucleus, either independently or in collaboration with other STIs" (Brazil, 2004, art. 16). This requirement aims to improve the innovation process by bringing STIs and companies closer together, with the TIC being responsible for managing the innovations generated and overseeing intellectual property protection policies, thus consolidating innovation policies.

In 2016, Law No. 13,243/2016, commonly known as the new legal framework for innovation, was enacted by the National Congress. This law introduced measures to promote innovation, extending to science and technology institutions and ensuring the formation of TIC to manage technologies developed in institutions conducting scientific research in Brazil, thus encompassing FI.

Thus, the update to Brazilian legislation had a positive impact on innovation. The legislation facilitated university-business (U-B) interaction, promoting institutional autonomy to establish partnerships with the private sector through joint research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) efforts, aiming to strengthen collaboration and innovation in Brazil (Paluma; Teixeira, 2019). The implementation of innovation-regulating laws is recent and still requires adjustments and reforms to eliminate barriers in U-B relations (Silva; Ribeiro; Barros, 2019).

- FIs and TTOs in the brazilian innovation ecosystem

The FI, established over a century ago as schools for apprentices and artisans (1909), have consistently aimed to provide professional training. Since 2008, as part of the government's growth acceleration program (PAC), they have expanded nationwide to over 661 units (Brasil, 2024), offering integrated secondary education, technology programs, and teacher training.

In addition to teaching, FI are tasked with "conducting applied research, fostering the development of technical and technological solutions, and extending these benefits to the community" (Law No. 11,892/2008, Art. 7, III). These institutions stand out for their high educational standards, underpinned by the tripod of teaching, research, and community outreach.

According to Mota, Araújo, and Santos (2018), the vocational training proposed by the FI allows for an integrated education that combines intellectual and manual work, in which the student incorporates the scientific, historical, and social dimensions into their specific technical activities. Ultimately, this training model aims to stimulate independent thinking, ensuring that individuals become accustomed to collective discipline and acquire the knowledge and skills that support their intellectual development.

In compliance with the LIT, by establishing the respective TIC within the FI, these entities are internally responsible for managing public innovation policies and strengthening the relationship between research and businesses, with each FI having its own exclusive TIC. According to Paluma and Teixeira (2019), the LIT and its modifications established the formation of TIC as a component of a public policy aimed at innovation in Brazil, with the goal of enhancing cooperation between the academic and private sectors. According to the annual report from the National Forum of Innovation and Technology Transfer Managers (FORTEC, 2023), based on data from 2022, one of the key highlights regarding innovation practices is the institutionalization and management of TIC. While some TIC are still in the implementation phase, positive development is being observed. The STIs are progressively incorporating TIC into their strategic planning and institutional management processes, with 90% of the TIC being integrated into the organizational direction of the institutions.

In the study entitled "Brazilian Education Policy and the Expansion of Federal Institutes", the authors pose critical questions regarding local and regional development, considering the investment in the expansion of FI by region. Another controversial point addresses the scope of the concepts and guidelines established for FI as government policies, as they assign these institutions the responsibility for offering various levels and modes of education, as if workforce training were the only solution to social problems (Prada; Garcia, 2016).

Regarding IP management in the STIs, the TIC are responsible for promoting strategies that foster an environment conducive to TT, overcoming the barriers related to the need for legislative adjustments, stimulating researchers and other stakeholders, and expanding the culture of disseminating technologies produced in academia (Fujino; Satl, 2007; Pires; Quitella, 2015).

Understanding the TT process between companies and schools (C-S) is part of the process for enabling the integration of Brazilian intellectual production into the daily lives of communities. Further changes are needed to strengthen the culture of innovation, public policies, and support for STIs aimed at the development of IP.

Methods

This study employed a quantitative approach and is classified as exploratory and descriptive. Exploratory research aims to become familiar with a subject that has been minimally explored (Gil, 2008). Descriptive research, on the other hand, can be understood as the observation and analysis of ordered data without interference from the researcher, allowing for the discovery of its frequency through interviews, forms, questionnaires, and observation (Pradanov & Freitas, 2013).

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committees (REC) of the State University of Santa Cruz (CAAE: 01517518.8.0000.5526), the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Ceará (CAAE: 01517518.8.3002.5589), and the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Southern Minas Gerais (CAAE: 01517518.8.3001.8158).

All 38 FI were contacted regarding their interest in participating in the research. Initially, 19 institutions agreed to participate, but 15 TIC ultimately completed the questionnaire, namely: FI Roraima, FI Tocantins, FI Bahia, FI Baiano, FI Maranhão, FI Piauí, FI Rondônia, FI Mato Grosso, FI Mato Grosso do Sul, FI Sul de Minas Gerais, FI Triângulo Mineiro, FI Espírito Santo, FI Rio de Janeiro, FI Catarinense, and FI Rio Grande do Sul.

For each TIC, one staff member associated with the sector was invited to respond to the research instrument. Each participant first signed a consent form and then sent a scanned copy to the lead researchers before completing the questionnaire. The information was gathered using a questionnaire created on the online platform Google

Forms, which was emailed to each participating TIC representative. Data collection took place from March to April 2019, with responses submitted via the form automatically received by the researchers. The questionnaire did not include any personal information about the respondents.

This study considered the following information and analyzed the corresponding responses regarding the structure of the TIC: a) The geographical region where the TIC headquarters is located (open question), classified into North, Northeast, Central-West, Southeast, and South; b) The year the TIC was established (open question), categorized based on the year 2016 following the enactment of Law No. 13.243; c) The workforce allocated to the TIC, considering administrative staff, interns, and scholarship holders (open question); d) The resources available to the TIC (furnished room, computers, internet, etc.); e) The identity territory(ies) in which the TIC is embedded (open question); f) The regulations governing IP at the institute (Law No. 10.973/2004 – Innovation Law; Law No. 13.243/2016 – New Legal Framework; Decree No. 5.563/2005 – Incentives for Innovation and Scientific and Technological Research in the Productive Environment; MCTI Ordinance No. 251/2014; others).

Regarding the performance of the TIC, the measured characteristics and corresponding response options were:

a) Competencies developed by the TIC (ensuring adherence to the institutional policy to stimulate protection of creations, licensing, innovation, and other forms of technology transfer; evaluating and classifying the results of research projects to comply with the provisions of this law; assessing requests from independent inventors for the adoption of inventions under Article 22; determining the appropriateness and promoting the protection of creations developed at the institution; evaluating the appropriateness of disclosing intellectual property-protectable creations developed at the institution; monitoring the processing of requests and the maintenance of the institution's IP titles; conducting studies on technological forecasting and competitive intelligence in the field of IP to guide the STIs innovation actions; developing studies and strategies for the transfer of innovations generated by the STIs; fostering and overseeing the STIs relationship with companies, particularly for activities covered under Articles 6 to 9; negotiating and managing technology transfer agreements from the STIs;

- b) Actions and projects developed by the TIC to promote and encourage research in the productive environment (open question); the frequency of actions that value scientific and technological research activities carried out at the institution (always; almost always; sometimes; rarely; never);
- c) The frequency of commercialization of technological innovations created at the institution (very frequently; frequently; rarely; very rarely; never);
- d) The number of established business partnerships (1-5; 6-10; over 10; none);
- e) The frequency of new business demands being developed at the institution (very frequently; frequently; rarely; very rarely; never);
- f) The tools used in the technology transfer process (creation of academic spin-offs; technology transfer contracts; training courses; agreements with other educational and/or research funding institutions; creation of technology-based incubators; others);
- g) The frequency of technology transfers directly to the local community (very frequently; frequently; rarely; very rarely; never).

The information on the TIC' geographic location and the time of their establishment was used to characterize the research sample. Data was stored in Microsoft Excel 2007 and analyzed using absolute and relative frequencies.

Results and discussion

Of the 19 FI that expressed interest in participating in this study, 15 TIC responded to the questionnaire. The remaining TIC did not respond to the survey and did not communicate their inability to participate. It is worth noting that all the institutions surveyed have TIC dedicated solely to meeting their institutional demands.

Figure 1 shows the geographical distribution of the participating FI, highlighting their locations. All five regions of Brazil were represented, which allowed for a more detailed characterization. Previous studies either focused on individual institutions or made regional comparisons with universities (Perucchi & Garcia, 2012; Chaves & Cruz, 2017; Rodrigues & Gava, 2016; Silva, Ribeiro & Barros, 2019).

Figure 1 – Map of the geographical distribution of the Federal Institutes in the research sample. 2019. Brazil.

Source: Author's own.

Regarding the length of time in operation, the average was approximately 7.33 years, considering the establishment dates of the TIC. The oldest was founded in 2005 (TIC of FI Bahia), and the newest in 2017 (TIC of FI Maranhão and FI Mato Grosso do Sul). It was observed that the majority (80%) of the TIC were created before the 2016 law 13.243, which classifies FI as STIs and mandates the establishment of TIC (Brasil, 2016).

According to data available on the Ministry of Education's website, this was likely triggered by the creation of Innovation Hubs through the partnership between the Brazilian Company for Industrial Research and Innovation (EMBRAPPII FI) and various industries, promoting interaction with R&D&I. In 2015, FI in Bahia, Ceará, Espírito Santo, Fluminense, and Minas Gerais pioneered this initiative, and in 2017, it was expanded to FI in Santa Catarina, Paraíba, Sul de Minas Gerais, and Goiano (Brasil, 2024).

Concerning the workforce available to work in the TIC, whether permanent staff (academic and administrative) or temporary (interns and scholarship holders), the average was around 5.6 people. It was noted that 53.3% of the TIC reported having one to three staff members, 26.7% had four to six, and 20% had ten or more. In most cases, TIC have small teams, though it is not possible to infer whether this number is insufficient. However, the lack of qualified human resources has been cited as the main management issue (Pires & Quitella, 2015; Rodrigues & Gava, 2016). The most significant internal challenge faced by the TIC is the absence of a permanent, qualified staff in innovation management and IP, which hampers the exchange of experience between institutions and companies and negatively impacts innovation policy (Chaves & Cruz, 2023).

The discrepancy in the number of staff members within TIC is likely due to differences in infrastructure organization adopted by the FI. Some institutions have expanded their TIC across multiple campuses, with these additional members contributing to the overall number of TIC personnel (Silva, Ribeiro & Barros, 2019).

Regarding the infrastructure provided by institutions for TIC operations, most reported having access to computers and the internet (31.9%, both), while 27.7% had exclusive, furnished offices. Four participants selected "other" for available resources but did not specify the tools. A study by Rodrigues and Gava (2016) identified that TIC in FI, unlike those in universities, often share space with other research departments. On one hand, this promotes synergy with the research sector, but on the other, it can discourage researchers due to the lack of necessary confidentiality. Fujino and Stal (2007) also noted that technology transfer offices often lack adequate infrastructure and autonomy, being internal units of universities immersed in conflicts of interest.

Table 1 presents the regulations governing IP in FI, allowing respondents to report as many relevant items as applicable. The Innovation Law was the most cited (27.4%), followed by the New Legal Framework (23.7%) and the Decree on Innovation and Technological Research Incentives (20%). These laws represent government efforts to promote and encourage research, development, and innovation activities, both in companies and academia, as they protect research outcomes and facilitate their

transfer to the market, a process that involves a complex set of institutional actions and decisions (Soares et al., 2016).

Additionally, there was mention of the "other" option (an open-ended response), where respondents cited internal resolutions approved by the institution's Superior Council (7.3%). The institutional policies regulating TIC actions are seen as key factors contributing to successful management and are present in most of the FI surveyed (Rodrigues & Gava, 2016). However, some studies indicated the need for updating these documents, which were outdated (Pires & Quintella, 2015). Therefore, it is possible that the majority of respondents did not mention the existence of internal resolutions due to recall bias.

Table 1 – Overview of regulations governing intellectual property at Federal Institutes of Education through Technology Innovation Centers. 2019. Brazil.

Response Options	AF*	RF (%)
Law No. 10,973/2004 – Innovation Law	15	27.4
Law No. 13,243/2016 – New Legal Framework	13	23.6
Decree No. 5,563/2005 – Incentives for Innovation and Scientific and Technological Research in Productive Environments	11	20.0
MCTI Ordinance No. 251/2014	7	12.7
Other: Decree No. 9,283/2018	4	7.3
Other: Resolutions approved by the institution's Superior Council	4	7.3
Other: Decree No. 9,279/1996	1	1.8
Total	55	100

Legend: AF - Absolute Frequencies; RF - Relative Frequencies; *Respondents could select more than one option, leading to a total exceeding the number of participants. **Source:** Author's own.

Table 2 presents the description of the competencies developed by the TIC, as outlined in the minimum competency requirements in article 16 of the New Legal Framework (Brazil, 2016). Respondents were allowed to select as many options as necessary. The competencies such as: ensuring the maintenance of institutional policies to encourage the protection of creations, licensing, innovation, and other forms of technology transfer; advising on the appropriateness of disseminating creations developed within the institution that are eligible for IP protection; and monitoring the processing of applications and the maintenance of the institution's intellectual property titles, were all identified as implemented by all participants (12.1% each). These findings support the data presented by Silva, Ribeiro, and Barros (2019), which highlighted the widespread implementation of most of the activities undertaken by TIC.

The competency relating to the development of studies and strategies for transferring innovation generated by the STIs was reported less frequently (7.3%). Although all activities are crucial to promoting innovation, scientific, and technological research within the productive sector to maximize the development of the national production system, the activities focused on fostering relationships with the productive environment were among the least employed by STIs (Silva; Ribeiro; Barros, 2019).

Table 2 - Description of competencies developed by the Technology Innovation Centers at Federal Institutes of Education. 2019. Brazil.

Response Options	AF*	RF (%)
Ensure the maintenance of institutional policies to encourage the protection of creations, licensing, innovation, and other forms of technology transfer	15	12.1
Assess and classify the outcomes of activities and research projects to ensure compliance with this Law	11	8.8
Evaluate requests from independent inventors regarding the adoption of an invention under Article 22	10	8.1
Advise on and promote the protection of creations developed within the institution	14	11.3
Advise on the appropriateness of disclosing creations developed within the institution that are eligible for intellectual protection	15	12.1
Monitor the processing of applications and the maintenance of the institution's intellectual property titles	15	12.1
Conduct technology prospecting studies and competitive intelligence in the field of intellectual property to guide the institution's innovation actions	10	8.1
Develop studies and strategies for transferring innovation generated by the institution	9	7.3
Promote and monitor the institution's relationship with companies, especially for activities outlined in Articles 6 to 9	12	9.7
Negotiate and manage technology transfer agreements arising from the institution's research	13	10.4
Total	124	100

Legend: AF - Absolute Frequencies; RF - Relative Frequencies; *Respondents could select more than one option, resulting in a total exceeding the number of participants. **Source:** Author's own.

Table 3 describes the actions and projects developed by TIC to promote and encourage research within the productive environment. Respondents could provide as much information as deemed necessary. Two participants left the question blank. A total of 17 actions were listed, and the most frequently mentioned internal practice was the launch of technological innovation calls, followed by the use of technology showcases and competency portfolios to establish strategies to promote agreements and partnerships.

To this end, institutional policies must promote and direct relationships with external environments, in addition to micro-institutional actions (Rodrigues; Gava, 2016). According to a study conducted by Machado, Sartori, and Crubellate (2017),

several actions adopted by TIC to foster and encourage research were identified: collaboration between universities and companies, providing advisory services to secure resources for R&D&I, coordinating business consultancy projects for industries, organizing events to train entrepreneurs, stimulating networks, and hosting talks to encourage innovation. They also mentioned organizing academic events on innovation and IP and awarding innovative projects.

Table 3 – Description of actions and projects developed by Technology Innovation Centers at Federal Institutes of Education to foster and promote research in the productive environment. 2019. Brazil.

- Talks with staff on what constitutes innovation and intellectual property protection.
- Launch of Technological Innovation Calls.
- Training and events on research, entrepreneurship, and technological innovation.
- Incubation projects, spin-offs, and innovation culture events.
- Technology prospecting with companies.
- Seeking and establishing partnerships.
- Use of technology showcases and competency portfolios to foster the creation of agreements and partnerships.
- Promotion of regional innovation exhibitions.
- Innovation Factory Project, which supports applied research and innovation projects developed within the institution, preferably in partnership with companies linked to local production arrangements (LPAs).
- Meetings with researchers and companies to organize partnerships.
- Creation of funding programs for research aimed at solving issues in local production arrangements (LPAs).
- Participation in the local Innovation Ecosystem.
- Member of the Management Committee of the Technology Park.
- Project to create the Integrated Innovation Projects System.
- Project to create a reference center for entrepreneurship and innovation.
- Development of innovation management and intellectual property software.
- Establishment of an intellectual property culture within the institution.

Source: Author's own.

To complement the discussion on actions and projects developed by TIC to promote and encourage research within the productive environment, participants were asked how often research activities were valued. The majority (53.4%) reported that this occurred "always", 33.3% indicated "almost always", and 13.3% answered "sometimes". None of the respondents selected "rarely" or "never". Although the effectiveness of these actions cannot be measured, it can be inferred that TIC regularly promote research activities.

In terms of the commercialization of innovative technological products developed within the institution, the majority (53.3%) reported that this had never occurred, followed by 26.7% who said it happened "rarely", 13.3% "very rarely", and 6.7% who indicated it occurred frequently. None of the respondents selected "very frequently". Regarding the number of partnerships established between the institution and external entities, 40% reported one to five partners, 33.3% indicated six to ten partners, 20% had more than ten partners, and 6.7% reported no external partnerships.

On the frequency of new external company demands for partnership, the majority (53.3%) stated that this occurred "rarely". Another 26.7% reported it "very rarely", and 20% indicated it happened "frequently". None selected "very frequently" or "never". When asked about the frequency of technology transfers directly to the local community, 40% reported it "very rarely", followed by 33.3% who said it had "never" occurred, and 26.7% who reported it happened "rarely." None of the participants selected "frequent" or "very frequent".

The lowest percentages highlighted above support previously discussed findings, considering the TIC average operating time of around 7.33 years, the qualifications of personnel, and internal challenges related to infrastructure and the execution of basic competencies, thus underscoring the fragility of TIC in FI. These characteristics add to the issues raised in the literature, such as the low levels of TT attributed to slow administrative processes in educational institutions, the lack of internal innovation regulations (Chaves; Cruz, 2023), the bureaucratic nature of intellectual property legislation, and the absence of a TT culture in Brazil (Garcez Júnior et al., 2016).

Table 4 provides a description of the tools used in the TT process by the TIC of FI, with respondents able to select as many options as necessary. The most used tool was the establishment of contracts/agreements with other educational and research funding institutions (28.6%), followed by the creation of technology-based incubators (25.9%) and training courses (20%). Additionally, "others" (open-ended responses) identified the use of a technology showcase as a tool (2.6%). One participant left this question blank.

The literature generally shows unsatisfactory results regarding TT contracts, and the disparity between the number of protection requests and the establishment of TT contracts highlights challenges in the commercial application of technologies and innovations registered by TIC (Garcez Júnior et al., 2016; Rodrigues; Gava, 2016; Silva; Ribeiro; Barros, 2019). Some authors suggest strengthening the entrepreneurial culture among students through the creation of technology-based incubators and academic spin-offs as strategies to facilitate technological development and the launch of innovations, thereby creating stronger connections with the business sector (Fujino; Stal, 2007; Pires; Quitella, 2015).

Table 4 – Characterization of the tools used in the technology transfer process by the Technology Innovation Centers of the Federal Institutes of Education. 2019. Brazil.

Response options	AF*	RF (%)
Creation of academic spin-offs	2	5.7
Technology transfer contracts	6	17.1
Training courses	7	20.0
Agreements/partnerships with other educational and/or research funding institutions	10	28.6
Creation of technology-based incubators	9	25.7
Others: Development of technology showcases	1	2.9
Total	35	100

Legends: AF - Absolute Frequencies; RF - Relative Frequencies; *The total number of responses exceeds the number of participants, as more than one option could be selected.

Source: Author's own data.

This study presents certain limitations, particularly regarding the sample composition, which only included a portion of the TIC within the FI, and did not encompass all active institutions in Brazil. However, it is important to highlight that TIC from all five regions of the country were represented, ensuring a diversified sample and providing a comprehensive overview of the national landscape concerning the TIC operations.

Additionally, considering the multicampus profile of the FI and the absence of TIC in all campuses, as the questionnaire was applied to the TIC located at the headquarters of the institutions, the operational dynamics and geographical distances between campuses might have posed some limitations. Nevertheless, the interaction between the TIC located at the headquarters and the campuses allows for the collection of comprehensive information about participating FI.

Final considerations

In conclusion, based on the structural information of the TIC, it was found that most have been in operation for a short period, with a limited staff and inadequate infrastructure provided by the FI. Furthermore, most TIC rely on Brazil's key legislation to guide their activities, with only a few instances of internal resolutions or regulations being used by the TIC to govern their operations.

Regarding the competencies developed by the TIC, none of the participants indicated that their TIC performs all the minimum competencies outlined in the New Legal Framework for Innovation, demonstrating a low performance concerning activities that foster external relations related to the development of the national production system. As for the main actions and projects carried out by the TIC to promote and incentivize research, the most frequent practices include the launch of technological innovation calls, and the use of technology showcases and competence portfolios to establish strategies for fostering partnerships and agreements.

In terms of formalizing C-S partnerships, commercializing innovative products created within the FI, developing new demands for companies, and transferring technology to the local community, these activities are not significantly represented, highlighting the weak connection with the market. The most frequently used tools in the technology transfer process by the TIC of the FI include agreements/partnerships with other educational and/or research funding institutions, the creation of technology-based incubators, and training courses are the most used tools in the TT process by the FI by TIC.

Overall, the activities of the TIC are essential for enabling technological innovation within the FI, as they provide a framework to develop a conducive environment for the promotion of IP and TT. Therefore, further studies on the process of institutionalization and the strengthening of the innovation culture are recommended, with a focus on finding ways to fortify the role of TIC within the FI.

Given the observations made, it is imperative to invest in infrastructure, streamline processes, grant greater autonomy to internal policies, and enhance the training of permanent staff to ensure the effective operation of TIC within the FI. This would enable the efficient transfer of innovative outputs, secure IP protection, and

foster institutional partnerships with companies, ultimately contributing to national economic development.

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